

OPPORTUNITIES FOR PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada inkluziv ta'lim tizimining barcha bosqichlari, shuningdek, keng imkoniyatlar haqida so'z boradi. Bundan tashqari, ta'limda tizimida olib borilayotgan keng ko'lamli islohotlar haqida fikr yuritiladi. Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida xalqaro aloqalar, ularning kelajakdagi istiqbollari haqida so'z yuritiladi. Inklyuziv ta'lim yo'nalishidagi malakali kadrlar tayyorlash va bu jarayondagi bir qator kamchiliklar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Inklyuziv ta'lim, ilmiy metod, xalqaro hamkorlikka doir aloqalar.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются все пункты системы инклюзивного образования, а также широкий спектр возможностей. В нем также рассматриваются более широкие реформы, которые происходят в системе образования. Система инклюзивного образования включает международные отношения и их будущие перспективы. Выделена подготовка квалифицированных кадров в области интеллектуального образования и ряд недостатков в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, научный метод, отношения по международному сотрудничеству

Abstract. This article discusses all the confuctio on the inclusive education system, as well as a wide range of possibilities. It also considers the broader reforms in the education system. The inclusive education system includes international relations and their future prospects. The training of qualified personnel in the field of intellectual education and a number of shortcomings in the process are highlighted.

Keywords: Inclusive education, scientific method, relations on international cooperation.

Social changes taking place at the current stage of society's development will lead to a change in attitudes towards education and upbringing of children, creating serious changes in the education system of our country. There are trends in the integration processes of general and special education, resulting in the problem of raising children with disabilities being one of the main ones. Early diagnosis and assistance to children in need of special education is becoming relevant for the implementation of the state system of scientific research and practice. Accordingly, psychological, medical and pedagogical assistance and support are needed for children of different age groups and categories, their surroundings, as well as other participants in the educational process. Article 41 of the U.S. Constitution states: "Everyone has the right to education. Getting free general education is guaranteed by the state. The fact that schoolwork is state-controlled" is also a great focus on education. In addition, it is noteworthy that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education is introduced into a separate mode and is devoted to inclusive education.

Article 20 of Uzbekistan constitution. Inclusive education is aimed at providing equal opportunities for all educators to study in educational institutions, taking into account the individual educational needs and the diversity of individual opportunities. Inclusive education is

organized in educational organizations for children (individuals) with physical, mental, sensory (sensory) or mental disabilities.

Psychological and pedagogical support for children in need of intellectual education involves correcting and socially adapting developmental disorders, creating the necessary frameworks for providing early correction assistance based on special pedagogical approaches and methods.

Children enrolled in inclusive education classes and primary correctional classes:

- children with hearing impairments (children with hearing loss up to 60 Db with no additional disorders);
- children with vision impairments (children with no additional visual impairments of up to 0.1);
- automatic diseases (children whose psychophysical and speech development rates do not correspond to age);
- children with severe speech defects (alalia, dyslalia, aphasia, rheumatism, dysarthria, weakness in the development of psychological and speech);
- children with disabilities in the base apparatus (children's cerebral disaster, scoliosis, polio, myopathy, osteomyelitis, amputation, neck growth deficiency — purity);
- children with disorders in the musculature system while preserving mental development;
- children whose mental development is preserved or who lag behind in spiritual development (children who can move themselves or move in additional settings and wheelchairs);
- children who lag behind in spiritual development with the potentially unspoiled possibilities of intellectual development;
- children with autistic spectrum without violations of behavior and morality;
- children whose intellectual development has been preserved, who are in a state of shock (if a child takes an anticonvulsant pill, the seizure is no more than 1st time in 1 month) [1].

It is necessary to create the most convenient conditions for these individuals by communicating and receiving a certain level and education in a certain direction, as well as by organizing inclusive education for children with special needs, including the social development of these students.

In recent years, a number of laws have been adopted in our country in the inclusive direction of education. These laws provide a wide range of opportunities for entities in need of inclusive education among the population.

The analysis of the laws showed that despite inclusive education being included as an educational form that excludes discrimination in any way against children with disabilities, the bill falls short of the inclusion provisions.

What does inclusive education mean?

The chairman of the U.S. Nursing Association, **Murod Isaac**, a member of the Council of Experts of the Senate Committee on Science, Education and Health, **emphasized the need to start by describing inclusive education** in the bill. He proposes to include the following definition in law:

“Inclusive education is to ensure equal access to knowledge in educational institutions, taking into account the special education needs and the difference of individual opportunities for all students”.

In order to ensure the intellectual right of each child to inclusive education (at all levels), the relevant state authorities must create the necessary conditions for all students, including children with disabilities and developmental disabilities in public schools.

"In order to support the student's personal system, the conditions must cover the presence of highly qualified pedagogical personnel, teachers (tutors) and other professionals who carry out their psychological and pedagogical companionship. "Conditions include the physical acceptance of buildings and structures, learning materials and technical equipment, the adaptation of curriculum based on an individual plan for student development, as well as the development and development of the institution's educational system for all students," explains Galina Nam [2].

Inclusive education is organized not only by mental or spiritual directions but also by physical science. It should be noted that opportunities should be provided for the development of these citizens not only mentally and morally but also physically.

It is reflected on the relationships of inclusive education in our country with international partners and their contributions to the development of the industry in this article.

UNICEF is responsible for introducing inclusive education into the U.S. education system. The objective of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all of them, regardless of their abilities or status. At the same time, the principle of inclusivity entails that children with disabilities must live in the family and learn at a normal school along with their peers in order to have positive spiritual and social development. The inclusive education system guarantees that a child in a wheelchair will be educated at any school nearby, have special assistance to learn to read and write if he or she is struggling to master, and that a child who does not attend classes will receive appropriate assistance to return to school [3].

Today, the UN sustainable development goals are known to serve as the basis for the criteria for development in all directions. Improving the quality of inclusive education and adapting it to the demands of time are among these objectives. A number of measures are also being taken at the National University of Uzbekistan to create favorable conditions for those with disabilities in each area and to update existing ones. The University's development strategy for 2022-2026 also outlines plans to further improve this network. During the recent Second French-U.S. Education Forum, it was previously reported that OMU professor Sh.Toshmatov had held talks with representatives of France's INSHEA (Institut national supérieur handicap et enseignements adaptés – National Institute for Education Adaptation for Persons with Disabilities) on inclusive education and had reached agreements on establishing cooperation. To implement these agreements, a video conference was held today, December 9, with Sophie Jint, a representative of the INSHEA leadership. The online dialogue focused on interacting with one another, improving teacher skills, promoting student mobility, ensuring the integrity of the inclusive education system not only in higher education but also from a young age, establishing interrelationships between stages of each era, and adapting educational institutions and their technical status to this type of education. At the end of the discussion, it was agreed that the OMU delegation would visit INSHEA educational institutions as the first phase of cooperation and that students would also participate.

Thus, the development and improvement of the system of supporting inclusive education will lead to the emergence of organizational, legal, methodological information and personnel problems in this educational model. In the field of personnel training:

- the need to deliver and qualitatively update the content of the inclusive education system in public schools;
- the lack of vocational training of pedagogical personnel and the inadequacy of vocational training for inclusive education, resulting in a number of problems in teaching children with special educational needs;
- lack of subjects related to the methodology of inclusive teaching in higher education programs in the field of pedagogy;
- the lack of inclusive teaching programs in textbooks on pedagogical and methodological sciences, as well as the fact that future teachers practice in educational institutions where children with special educational needs are involved has a negative impact on the quality of their professional preparation;
- the ineffectiveness of the introduction of inclusive education as a result of the lack of adequate information about inclusive education by the leadership and pedagogical standards of secondary schools;
- training courses for children with specialized educational needs have not been established in training and rehabilitation institutions, and the introduction of modern information communication technologies for inclusive education in their work [4];

Instead, it should be noted that today a number of innovations are being made in all areas of education in our country, including the inclusive direction. Subjects in need of inclusive education are supported not only spiritually but also materially. A number of decisions are being made to provide these citizens with continuous education. Foreign experts have also been involved in the development of this field and the training of professional personnel, from wour young staff are studying qualifications and methods.

REFERENCES

1. S.Mo‘minov, Sh.Axmedov, G.Alimova. Inklyuziv ta’limning barcha subyektlari uchun psixologik-pedagogik va rivojlantirishga yo‘naltirilgan texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish va takomillashtirib borish. –T: Toshkent 2022. (For all subjects of inclusive education psychological-pedagogical and development of oriented technologies and their improvement)
2. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2020/06/09/education-law/>
3. <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/uz/inklyuziv-talim>
4. <https://nuu.uz/inklyuziv-talim-boyicha-fransiya-bilan-hamkorlik/>